

duced radium into the larynx in the treatment of a papilloma in a young child. In another infant radium was applied to the outside of the larynx. He does not know the dosage because he did not own the radium.

DR. THOMAS J. HARRIS confirmed what Dr. Levy had said with reference to the simplicity of the method in children and the wonderful view of the larynx obtained in the average case. He referred briefly to a case in which he applied radium in a child, 6 years of age, using the suspension apparatus, with rectal anesthesia, one hundred milligrams of radium, of one million activity, being applied for twenty minutes. The first time he attempted to apply the radium, without the suspension apparatus, he thought it went into the esophagus instead of into the larynx. When the apparatus was employed it was very much easier to see the papilloma and to make the application of radium. He recommended the use of rectal anesthesia in these cases.

DR. LEVY, in closing the discussion, said that he had not found the report of Dr. Yankauer's case in his search for all cases to date in which suspension laryngoscopy had been employed in children. He thought the old Killian method of suspension apparatus better in children, but in adults he liked the Albrecht or Howorth modification. He had used cocain in adults, but in children he used general anesthesia. Morphine and hyoscin in cases in which a large percentage of cocain did not seem to abolish the laryngeal reflex were useful in adults. He has never been able to see why adrenalin was added to the cocain, inasmuch as it is not an anesthetic and as there is very little loss of blood in these cases. In some cases of children with chloroform anesthesia, the adductors contracted, the vocal bands came together, and the spasm of the larynx continued for some time. In such cases a dilute solution of cocain was of advantage.

The Clinical Significance of Bacteremia. DR. JOHN E. SHEPPARD, Brooklyn.

Four cases are reported, which seemed to the author to be fairly illustrative of a considerable series of cases encountered at the Jewish Hospital in Brooklyn. The four cases and others of the group from which these were selected, would appear to demonstrate that not all cases of otitic bacteremia need operation. To distinguish between cases which do and those which do not require operation calls for one's closest observation and best judgment.

As aids, all too meager at times it is true, in coming to a conclusion as to whether or not to operate, the author suggests the following points: (1) The general condition and appearance of the patient. Is there a markedly septic condition? Is it increasing or decreasing? As of the greatest aid in determining this, (2) The temperature curve. (3) Whether the process is localizing or tending to become general. (4) Blood counts, frequent enough to keep a careful line on the patient's resisting power. (5) Blood cultures, sufficiently often to have a definite knowledge of the persistence of the organism in the blood, and whether the number of colonies per cubic centimeter is increasing or diminishing, thus showing whether or not the patient is in need of assistance in taking care of the bacteremia.

DISCUSSION.

DR. ARTHUR B. DUEL thought the interesting reports of Dr. Sheppard served to emphasize certain principles in infectious processes which were of great clinical importance. It must be evident that in all infections the general clinical symptoms usually noted are the result of the action of bacteria or their products which have been poured into the circulation. When the general clinical manifestations are slight, the infecting focus is confined to an unfavorable locality for getting into the circulation, or the invading organism is slightly virulent. Thus, a follicular tonsillitis of streptococcic origin will produce much more violent manifestations than a streptococcic otitis or mastoiditis. Similarly, a staphylococcic follicular tonsillitis, being in a favorable field for pouring its products into the circulation, may cause considerable general upset (though comparatively less than its more virulent cousins), while, confined to a bony cavity, it may cause hardly enough disturbance to be recognized. Whatever manifestation there may be, however, is undoubtedly caused by the bacterial invasion of the circulation. It may be asked, then, why bacteremia is not always demonstrable in suppurative conditions. The answer is two-fold. In the first place, the methods of examination are not sufficiently delicate; in the second place, most of the organisms are destroyed almost immediately by the blood cells. Only a few of the most virulent type are able to live and multiply in the circulation.

Is a demonstrated bacteremia, then, of no value as an operative indication? Of course it may be of the greatest value. In a case, for example, in which bacteremia is demonstrated, where the blood count shows a low resistance, and where the patient is doing badly, the obvious thing to do is to localize the process—to cut off the blood stream at that point without regard to whether or not there is a demonstrable disintegrating clot. In fact, in his opinion, to look upon bacteremia alone in suppurative otitis or mastoiditis as indicative of septic sinus thrombosis is unwarranted. The bacteremia always precedes the clot-formation—indeed, the alteration of the vessel wall by bacterial invasion is essential to the formation of the clot. At this stage it may not be always demonstrable by present methods, but theoretically it is present, and if methods of investigation were nice enough, it might possibly be demonstrated a day before, or, perhaps, a week before, a recognizable clot has formed.

Of course, after the clot has formed and has begun to disintegrate, the chance of demonstrating a bacteremia is much greater, because the infecting focus is in the most favorable situation for the constant discharge of large numbers of organisms into the circulation. Yet, with a patient doing badly, one might feel quite justified in isolating the infecting area, whether bacteremia could or could not be shown. On the other hand, with the patient doing very well, the demonstration of a bacteremia might not necessarily demand an operation. Hundreds, of course, recover every year without it having been thought necessary to demonstrate the bacteremia, which is undoubtedly present. One should carefully avoid taking too narrow a view of the clinical significance of bacteremia.

DR. CHARLES W. RICHARDSON considered the demonstration of bacteremia an important point in the history of all cases of probable sinus infection.

Whether a positive bacteremia is always indicative of sinus thrombosis is a question still subject to considerable dispute. In cases on the borderline, as it were, the condition of the blood is of much value to the clinician, and should be of great assistance in deciding whether operative intervention is demanded. Without clear and definite indications from a clinical point of view there is no doubt that many would be loath to go into the sinus, although the experiences of Grünings and others seem to demonstrate that in cases of simple bacteremia, without very pronounced clinical symptoms, there may be sinus thrombosis. How far one would be warranted, with the evidence of bacteremia and without clinical evidences of sinus thrombosis, in delaying operative intervention is a question. With bacteremia, even without clinical evidence, he would be loath to delay. Dr. Sheppard's cases were almost negative, in a certain sense, especially his non-operative cases, in which he was fortunate, in that they recovered without operative intervention.

DR. SEYMOUR OPPENHEIMER was under the impression that Dr. Duel and his confreres at the Manhattan Eye and Ear Hospital were no longer at variance with Dr. Libman and Dr. Celler and others at the Mount Sinai Hospital, with reference to this question of bacteremia. At Mount Sinai it was held that acute otitis *per se* never caused bacteremia, and these views had been corroborated by the clinical findings. This difference of opinion was thought to be largely a matter of variance in laboratory technic, the fact that the Manhattan Eye and Ear Hospital reached different conclusions being considered at Mount Sinai to be due to some error in laboratory technic. He and his associates at the latter institution had not changed their view-point at all, being still of the opinion that suppurative otitis *per se* does not cause bacteremia. They were also of the opinion that demonstrable bacteremia is a clinical expression of sinus thrombosis. Up to the present time, they had from ninety to ninety-five cases of sinus thrombosis in which bacteremia had been demonstrated in advance of operation, and in not one case had the operation failed to demonstrate sinus thrombosis. It was a curious fact that if they were wrong in their deductions, they were able to demonstrate conclusively, a few hours after operation, that the blood culture became sterile, showing that the operative procedure must have attacked some local focus which was responsible for the infection. In two hours, in some instances, the blood had become sterile. In some cases the blood culture still remained positive, but there were other explanations, such as vegetations on the heart valves secondary to the initial infection.

DR. S. MACCUEEN SMITH asked Dr. Oppenheimer whether he depended upon the blood cultures for indications for operation, or whether he was guided by other symptoms of the disease.

DR. WILLIAM B. CHAMBERLAIN said he understood Dr. Sheppard to say that he opened the lateral sinus but made no mention of ligating the jugular. He could see no reason, under the circumstances, for not immediately ligating the jugular.

DR. EWING W. DAY called attention to one point that seemed to have been overlooked. There is a tendency to take for granted that every lateral sinus patient, unless operated upon, dies. If a patient with thrombosis gets well it is no indication that the sinus is not blocked. He has

had cases in which the sinus was completely obliterated by clot, and he can not say that if the patient gets well there is no clot.

DR. OPPENHEIMER, continuing the discussion, in answer to Dr. Smith's question, said that he had been particularly cautious, by reason of these controversies, not to be too enthusiastic. Many cases had been admitted to the hospital with but fewest of otitic symptoms, with suggestions of typhoid fever possibly, with no symptoms of mastoiditis, but with a positive blood culture. He had been extremely cautious in saying that he was dealing with infectious phlebitis, and had deferred operating until all other possible causes had been ruled out. Invariably they had found a thrombotic condition in the sinus.

Answering a question by Dr. George L. Richards as to whether all his ninety or ninety-five cases were operated upon, he said they were.

DR. WENDELL C. PHILLIPS verified Dr. Day's statements. He had been struck, years ago, in operative surgery on the ear, to find occasionally an obliterated sinus from an old sinus thrombosis.

DR. JOHN A. THOMPSON recalled having treated a brother laryngologist for suppurative ethmoiditis. He developed an abscess in the big toe which was opened under antiseptic precautions, and examination of the pus revealed the presence of streptococci. The nasal sinuses are sometimes at fault in bacteremia.

DR. SHEPARD, in closing the discussion, said he simply reported four cases as a part of a group of cases of bacteremia, many of the group being cases which had been operated upon. Regarding the tying of the jugular, he had rather settled down to the rules of not tying it if there is a reasonably good return-flow from the bulb. Should there be no return flow he waited a day or two and then tied off the jugular. It was probably true, as Dr. Richardson suggested, that he was fortunate in not having had results. Possibly more than simple good fortune is indicated by the fact that the cases referred to were selected from perhaps fifty or more cases of bacteremia, of which he had kept careful records, and of which twenty-five at least had not been operated upon. Dr. Thompson referred to other sources of bacteremia. This fact needs to be kept in mind. He very decidedly does not advocate operating upon all cases of bacteremia. Dr. Oppenheimer spoke of his cases as being cases of suppurative otitis. Three of the cases reported in the paper were non-suppurative otitis. He questions the necessity of operating upon all these cases if they are properly watched, especially if in conjunction with a practical bacteriologist. He thinks that more extensive observations would ultimately teach in which cases to operate and in which surgical intervention is not necessary.

Treatment of Purulent Cerebrospinal Meningitis. DR. WILLIAM SOHIER BRYANT, New York. The object of this communication is to apply the experience of an unusually successful case to the management of this infection.

The treatment of purulent-septic meningitis consists of (1) treatment for relief of the intra-cranial pressure; (2) treatment of the toxemia; (3) treatment of the focal infection. The goal of the treatment is the control of intra-cranial pressure and toxemia, and the treatment should, there-